

FEATURES OF TEACHING SHORT RUNNING TECHNIQUES

Boborakhmatov Bobir Buriyevich

Lecturer at the Faculty of Sports Activities and Management

Termez State University

Annotation: In the pack, the features of teaching the technique of sprinting are considered. Tasks and means for their solution are determined. The stages of training in running technique are divided, as well as the methods used in training.

Key words: sprinting, running technique training, correct running skills formation.

Introduction. The technique of sprinting is purely individual and, despite certain biomechanical characteristics, depends on the specific individual characteristics of the athlete, as well as on the levels of power and speed achieved by him. This, of course, does not exclude the common for all rational elements of technique, the improvement of which athletes are constantly engaged in [1, 2].

Learning any motor action obeys the basic principles and goes through a number of stages [3]. Currently, there are several well-known teaching methods. The traditional methodology, based on learning a motor action in parts, is consistent with the basic principles of "from simple to complex" and "from the main to the secondary" and has two directions [4, 5]. First: at the initial stage, one should teach in parts, phases. The second direction is holistic training in motor action [6].

The teaching methodology presents tasks and means of solving them, methods of using exercises, ways of organizing a lesson and performing exercises, the number of repetitions of exercises, or their dosage [7, 8, 9]. That is, the learning objectives tell us what we are going to teach, the means by which, methods - how to teach, as well as what you need to know to perform this or that exercise, and how to organize the process of performing the exercise itself. When training and improving the

technique of sprinting, knowledge of the basic patterns of the formation of motor skills is necessary [10, 11, 12]. The process of mastering movements takes place in three stages:

- familiarization with the new movement,
- formation of the basics of technology;
- formation of motor skills;
- motor skill formation [13, 14].

At the familiarization stage, you need to create an idea of the movement that needs to be mastered; the range of means used can be the most diverse: the teacher's explanation, the showing of cinematographs, videos, the demonstration of running by qualified athletes, the performance of a test run by those involved.

At the stage of motor skill formation, it is necessary to bring the performance of all technical elements of sprinting to a relatively perfect form by repeated repetitions, correcting and correcting the errors that occur [15, 16].

At the stage of formation of a motor skill, one should bring the performance of the movement to relative perfection, be able to demonstrate the technique of movement in changing conditions, including competitive ones [17, 18]. In the learning process, one must be guided by general pedagogical, didactic principles of consciousness, activity, visibility, accessibility and strength [19, 20].

Training in sprinting technique does not occur in the same sequence as in teaching other types of athletics, since running is a natural way for a person to move quickly. However, the technique of sports running differs significantly in its effectiveness from the technique of ordinary running and requires the preservation of natural freedom of movement. Next, we will recommend a set of exercises to improve the technique of sprinting, introduce a set of exercises to improve the low start, starting run, distance running and finishing.

The traditional method of teaching sprinting is as follows.

- Create an idea of the correct technique for running short distances.

- Teach the technique of running in a straight line. The main attention is on the free and correct execution of the elements of running (work of the arms, legs, position of the torso, head).
- Teach the technique of low start and starting acceleration. To teach the rational arrangement of starting blocks, taking into account the individual characteristics of those involved.
- Teach finishing technique.
- To improve the technique of sprinting in general.

Breathing rhythm is essential in sprinting. With a low running speed, one respiratory movement (inhalation and exhalation) is performed in 6 steps. With increasing speed, the frequency of breathing increases; one breathing movement is performed in 4, and sometimes in 2 steps. Speed, amplitude of movements, manifestation of muscular efforts depend on the speed of running (the higher the speed, the higher the values of the listed factors). An increase in running speed due to an increase in stride length is limited, since too large a step requires large energy costs. The stride length of runners is approximately 160-220 centimeters, depending on the distance and individual characteristics. Running speed is usually increased by the frequency of steps while maintaining their length.

One of the main indicators of running technique is the power of effort and the efficiency of movements. As the distance increases, the value of the efficiency factor of movements prevails over the value of the work power factor, since the length and frequency of steps decrease.

One of the main indicators of the correct running technique is the absence of vertical shaking of the head. This moment should be given special attention and work on a smooth, without hesitation of the head, moving forward.

To increase the running speed, it is necessary, firstly, to work on reducing the support time, i.e. with the same repulsion force, reduce the repulsion time. Since the periods of support and transfer are related to each other, a decrease in the support time will also cause a decrease in the transfer time and vice versa, that is, a quick

reduction of the hips and a quick extension of the hip of the fly leg forward will reduce the transfer time and, therefore, will help to quickly take off in less time. A quick “removal” of the pushing leg from the support after repulsion also speeds up its transfer forward. It is desirable that all efforts in running be directed towards moving forward, so the head, along with the body of the athlete, should move horizontally. If the repulsion is directed significantly upwards, then the run turns out as if in jumps, from foot to foot. A similar thing occurs when the idea of technique is reduced to a vigorous spread of the legs to the moment of the final position of the running step. The torso tilt also depends on the running speed. A large incline will result in a shorter stride length.

Conclusions. Thus, sprint competitions, in addition to a high level of endurance, also require versatile training in overcoming obstacles, a quick analysis of the situation that has arisen and its adequate solution. A runner who has mastered a variety of techniques realizes his potential more fully in competitions.

References:

1. Burievich, B. B. (2022). Improvement of Speed and Strength Abilities in Young Middle Distance Runners. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 661-664.
2. Babarakhmatov, B. B. (2022). Role of the trainer in the psychological training of the athlete in outschool work on physical education and sport. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 2(106), 206-209.
3. Buriyevich, B. B. (2022). Features of the Training Process of Young Athletes at the Initial Stage of Preparation. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 1(9), 103-107.
4. Boborakhmatov, B. (2022). Initial training of young athletes in the conditions of a sport class. *Models and methods in modern science*, 1(13), 70-74.
5. Burievich, B. B. (2022). Role of the Trainer in the Psychological Training of the Athlete in Out-School Work on Physical Education and Sport. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 29–32.

6. Burievich, B. B. (2022). Conditions for forming skills to perform a low start in short distance run. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(04), 525-528.
7. Бабарахматов, Б. Б. (2020). Подготовка будущих учителей физической культуры к инновационной деятельности. *Матрица научного познания*, (6), 403-407.
8. Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2022). Формирование у подростков волевых качеств в процессе физического воспитания. *Science and Education*, 3(7), 283-289.
9. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2022, September). Formation of moral and volitional qualities of adolescents by means of physical education. In *International scientific conference "Innovative trends in science, practice and education"* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 198-204).
10. Turdimurodov, D. (2022). Volitional qualities of a person and their formation in adolescent age. *Models and methods in modern science*, 1(14), 13-17.
11. Турдимуродов, Д. (2022). Жисмоний тарбия дарси мактаб ўқувчиларида иродавий сифатларни ривожлантирувчи восита сифатида. *Общество и инновации*, 3(6/S), 74-80.
12. Абдуллаев Я. М., Турдимуродов Д. Й. Создание педагогических условий в формировании волевых качеств у учеников начальных классов / Я. М. Абдуллаев, Д. Ю. Турдимуродов // *Colloquium-journal*. - 2020. -№ 24-2(76). -С. 14-16.
13. Абдуллаев Я. М., & Турдимуродов Д. Й. (2020). Ўсмир ёшдаги ўқувчиларда иродавий сифатларни жисмоний тарбия воситалари орқали ривожлантириш. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (9 (94)), 56-62.
14. Alikulovich M. K., & Yuldashevich T. D. (2020). Development of physical training skills and formation of willpower qualities in extracurricular activities. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 8(3).
15. Menglikulov Khayrulla Alikulovich. (2022). The significance of psychological preparation of young swimmers. *Proceedings of International Conference on Scientific Research in Natural and Social Sciences*, 1(1), 84–88.

16. Менгликулов, Х. А. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, *Учредители: Общественная организация" Институт социальной трансформации*, 104-107.
17. Менгликулов, Х. (2022). 14-15 ёшдаги сузувчиларда тезлик-куч сифатларини ривожлантириш услубиёти. *Общество и инновации*, 3(6/S), 81-87.
18. Makhkamovich, A. Y. (2022). Mobile Games Among Children in Pedagogical Practice. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 1(9), 90-94.
19. Менгликулов Хайрулла Аликулович (2022). Ёш сузувчиларни ўргатишнинг бошланғич босқичида танловнинг назарий жиҳатлари. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (8 (117)), 55-59.
20. Alikulovich, M. K. (2022). Method of developing speed-strength qualities in young swimmers 12-14 years. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4, 179-182.